

Role of Amino Groups in the Biological Activity of Cardiotoxin II

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The importance of free amino groups in the biological activity of cardiotoxin II was assessed using 2,4-pentanedione as the modifying agent. The amino groups were modified to enamines by 2,4-pentanedione. The modification was completely reversed at low pH or on addition of hydroxylamine. All ten amino groups, nine side chain and one α -amino group were modified by the reagent, as judged by spectro-photometric data. On modification of the amino groups of cardiotoxin II, there was progressive loss of both lethal toxicity and the ability to protect bacterial protoplasts against lysis. The two activities decayed in almost parallel manner. In the presence of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) the modification of amino groups was hindered. SDS interfered in the assay of bacterial cell lysis induced by lysozyme. The present study further revealed that both α - and ϵ -amino groups in the proteins and amino acids were accessible for modification with 2,4-pentanedione.

CARDIOTOXINS are basic proteins found in the venom of cobra. They constitute more than 30 per cent of the venom constituents. They are well acknowledged for their membrane disorganising property¹. Recent studies revealed yet another property of cardiotoxin II, viz. stabilisation of bacterial protoplasts by the toxin².

Chemical modification studies on biologically active proteins are carried out in delineating amino acid side-chains which are important for their structure and function³. Such studies on toxic components of cobra venoms have been extensively done on the post-synaptic neurotoxins⁴. However, a few studies have been carried out on cardiotoxins⁵⁻⁹. The importance of side-chain amino groups of lysine residues for the biological activity of cardiotoxins has been suggested as the toxin binds only to negatively charged phospholipids and not to positively charged or zwitterionic phospholipids of the liposome vesicles¹⁰. The presence of positive charges on the cardiotoxin molecules by virtue of its exceptionally high content of lysine residues do possibly help in the initial binding to the cell membrane. However, there is no direct evidence to show the importance of amino groups in the biological activity of cardiotoxins except for one report, wherein, the ability of *N,N'*-dimethyl cardiotoxin to displace ³⁵S-labelled cardiotoxin from the heart cell membrane was shown to be diminished and lacking in toxic potency¹¹. Although the report does not give detailed study on the modified toxin. The present paper deals with the observations on the role of free amino groups in the biological activity of cardiotoxin II. Primary amines react with 2,4-pentanedione at pH 6-9 to form enamines, *N*-alkyl-4-amino-4-penten-2-ones, which can be made to yield back the original primary

amine on treatment at low pH or with hydroxylamine¹². Guanidines and substituted guanidines also react with the reagent to form *N*-substituted-2-amino-4,6-dimethylpyrimidines but at a rate which is lower by at least a factor of 20 than the rate of 2,4-pentanedione with primary amines¹³. Unlike the reaction of 2,4-pentanedione with primary amines which is reversible, the reaction with guanidines is irreversible¹⁴. The advantage of differential reactivities of 2,4-pentanedione with primary amines and guanidines was exploited in modifying the free amino groups in cardiotoxin II. Earlier report¹⁵, did not stress on the reactivity of ϵ -amino groups in amino acids and proteins with the reagent. In the present paper, this aspect is also investigated.

Experimental

Cardiotoxin II was purified from the venom of Indian cobra (*Naja naja*) as described earlier¹⁶. Lyophilised sample of *Micrococcus lysodeikticus* cells (Sigma), egg-white lysozyme (a gift from Societta Prodotti Antibiotici, Milano), 2,4-pentanedione (B.D.H., U. K.) and 1-fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (FDNB) (Koch Light) were used. Other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Measurements involving light absorption were done with a MSE Spectro Plus MK1 A or a Colemann Junior 6A spectrophotometer.

Preparation of N-n-butyl-4-amino-3-penten-2-one: The compound was prepared by the reaction of 2,4-pentanedione with *n*-butylamine as described earlier¹⁴. The molar absorption in 0.1 M phosphate buffer at 310 nm was found to be $2.05 \times 10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ (lit. $2.1 \times 10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$).

Preparation of δ -(4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidyl) ornithine : It was prepared essentially as described earlier^{1a}. Yield was 0.131 g (4.2%) (lit. 10%). The m.p. observed was 268° (lit. 269-270°) and the molar absorption at 300 nm was $3.9 \times 10^5 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (lit. $3.4 \times 10^5 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Reaction of L-lysine with 2,4-pentanedione : To L-lysine (1.6 mg) in 0.1 M borate buffer (1 ml) pH 9.5 was added 2,4-pentanedione to give a concentration of 0.4 M. The solution was mixed on a shaker for 2 h and taken to dryness in vacuum. The residue was redissolved in distilled water and then dried again. The process was repeated twice more to remove any traces of 2,4-pentanedione remaining in the product. The derivative was diluted with 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 7.0 to give a concentration of about $0.01 \mu \text{ mol ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorption and the spectrum of the resulting product was determined. The molar absorption at 310 nm was found to be $4.2 \times 10^4 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (equivalent of two amino groups modified, ϵ for each amino group modified being $2.1 \times 10^4 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The uv spectrum showed an absorbance maximum at 300 nm. The amino acid was completely regenerated on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride as judged by the disappearance of the peak at 310 nm.

Modification of amino groups in cardiotoxin II with 2,4-pentanedione : Modification of amino groups was carried out as described earlier^{1a}. However, the method was slightly altered, in that, instead of subjecting the modified derivative to gel-filtration to stop the reaction and remove excess reagent, the reaction mixture was immediately frozen at -50° in an ethylene glycol bath and freeze-dried. Cardiotoxin II (1 mg ml^{-1}) was reacted with 0.1 or 0.2 M 2,4-pentanedione contained in 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 8.0 or 0.1 M borate buffer pH 9.5. The reaction was carried out both in the presence and absence of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS). At different time intervals suitable aliquots ($40 \mu\text{l}$) were withdrawn from the reaction mixture and immediately subjected to freeze-drying. The dried material was redissolved in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (3 ml) containing 0.01% SDS and the absorbance was measured at 310 nm. The extent of modification was followed by measuring the increase in absorbance at 310 nm. The number of amino groups reacted was calculated using a molar absorption for product of $2.1 \times 10^4 M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, per amino group modified. The reaction was completely reversed in the presence of 0.1 M hydroxylamine hydrochloride, as verified by the disappearance of the characteristic peak at 310 nm. To check if the arginines in cardiotoxin II were also modified, the absorbance at 300 nm of the modified derivative after complete reversal with hydroxylamine was measured.

Dinitrophenylation of the modified and native cardiotoxin II : To verify if the α -amino group in cardiotoxin II was also reacted with 2,4-pentanedione, a completely modified derivative was dinitrophenylated using fluordinitrobenzene (FDNB)

essentially as described earlier^{1a}. To cardiotoxin II (native and fully modified) (2 mg) and an equal amount of NaHCO_3 , was added distilled water (0.2 ml) and FDNB solution (0.2 ml) (5% v/v in ethanol). The dinitrophenylated derivative was precipitated with concentrated HCl. However, the derivative fully modified with 2,4-pentanedione was not precipitated on addition of the acid. Excess FDNB was removed by ether extraction, and the precipitate (with native cardiotoxin II) was washed with ethanol, water and acetone. The sample was then dried in air and suspended in constant boiling 5.7 N HCl (0.5 ml) and subjected to hydrolysis in an evacuated tube at 110° for 20 h. The modified derivative which did not precipitate on addition of HCl was extracted with ether to remove the excess FDNB and dried over NaOH and P_2O_5 in vacuum. The residue was subjected to acid hydrolysis as was done for native cardiotoxin. The hydrolysed sample was diluted to 1 N in strength with distilled water and extracted with ether. Combined ether extracts were pooled and evaporated in a stream of air and the residue redissolved in acetone ($50 \mu\text{l}$). The aqueous phase was taken to dryness in vacuum over NaOH and P_2O_5 , and redissolved in water ($50 \mu\text{l}$). The DNP-amino acids were identified by thin layer chromatography (tlc) using silica gel-G as adsorbent. Ether soluble DNP-amino acids were identified using two-dimensional tlc, the first dimension was run with solvent system toluene-pyridine-2-chloroethanol-0.8 NH_4OH (100 : 30 : 60 : 60, v/v) and the second dimension with benzene-pyridine-acetic acid (80 : 20 : 2, v/v). The water-soluble DNP-amino acid was separated in a single-dimension using n-butanol-25% NH_4OH (80 : 20, v/v). The amount of DNP-amino acid was quantitated by measuring the absorbance at 360 nm of sample spots eluted with 1% NaHCO_3 solution. The DNP-amino acids were identified by running appropriate standards along with the sample.

Toxicity test : The lethality of modified cardiotoxin II was checked by injecting (intra-peritoneally) appropriate amounts of the sample into Swiss albino mice. Samples were dissolved in 0.9% saline (0.5 ml) and injected into mice which were kept under observation for 72 h thereafter. In cases where samples were insoluble, owing to a high extent of modification, 0.01% SDS was incorporated for achieving solution. LD_{50} was determined as described earlier^{1a}.

Assay of bacterial cell lysis : The ability of modified cardiotoxin II to inhibit bacterial cell lysis was done essentially as described earlier^{1a}. The inhibition caused by cardiotoxin II at $0.0457 \mu \text{ mol ml}^{-1}$ level was assumed to be 100% and the inhibition of lysis by the modified derivative was calculated on this assumption.

Results

Modification of amino groups in cardiotoxin II with 2,4-pentanedione : The reaction of free amino

groups in cardiotoxin II was favoured by higher pH as is evident from Fig. 1. In 0.1 M phosphate buffer pH 8.0, the reaction does not lead to modification of all the amino groups. At 0.1 and 0.2 M concentrations, 2,4-pentanedione modifies only 5.9 and 7.1 amino groups, respectively, in 4 h. There was no further modification in 24 h thereafter. In 0.1 M borate buffer pH 9.5, modification of all the ten amino groups occurs, within 3 h. In the presence of SDS and 0.2 M reagent the modification of amino groups was very much hindered. In 4 h,

Fig. 1. Reaction of amino groups in cardiotoxin II with 2,4-pentanedione under varying conditions: (O) and (Δ) in phosphate buffer 0.1 M, pH 8.0, (●) in phosphate buffer 0.1 M, pH 8.0 containing 0.01% SDS and (□) in borate buffer 0.1 M, pH 9.5. The values in parenthesis indicate the concentration of 2,4-pentanedione.

Fig. 2. UV spectra of lysine derivative with 2,4-pentanedione: (—) modified lysine ($0.0113 \mu \text{ mol ml}^{-1}$); (---) modified lysine in the presence of 0.1 M hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Fig. 3. UV spectra in phosphate buffer 0.1 M, pH 7.0, containing 0.01% SDS of: (●) native cardiotoxin II ($113 \mu \text{ g ml}^{-1}$), (○) cardiotoxin II ($22 \mu \text{ g ml}^{-1}$) with all amino groups modified and (---) fully modified cardiotoxin II ($22 \mu \text{ g ml}^{-1}$) on treatment with 0.1 M hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

about two amino groups are modified, whereas six amino groups are modified in 24 h (Fig. 1). In the absence of SDS, in phosphate buffer, seven amino groups could be modified in 4 h. The characteristic uv spectrum of the modified derivative is shown in Figs. 2 and 3. It is evident that the modification is completely reversible on addition of hydroxylamine hydrochloride to a concentration of 0.1 M, with the loss of the characteristic peak at 310 nm. That under the conditions employed arginine residues were not affected, is revealed by the absence of the absorption maximum characteristic of the arginine derivative and which cannot be abolished by hydroxylamine.

Dinitrophenylation of native and modified cardiotoxin II: The dinitrophenylation studies on cardiotoxin II (native and modified) revealed that all amino groups including the α -amino group were modified by 2,4-pentanedione. Therefore, these groups were not accessible for dinitrophenylation. The yield of N-terminal leucine was about 0.4 mol mol⁻¹ (uncorrected) for native cardiotoxin II. No N-terminal leucine was detectable in fully modified cardiotoxin II.

Toxicity test: LD₅₀ determination (Table 1) revealed that modification of amino groups with 2,4-pentanedione resulted in gradual diminution of

TABLE 1—LD₅₀ DETERMINATION OF NATIVE AND MODIFIED CARDIOTOXIN II

No. of amino groups modified	LD ₅₀ mg/kg mouse	Retention of lethality %
0	2.8	100
1	3.9	71
2	8.2	34
3	9.8	28
4	16.8	16
5*	—	0

* Not active at as high a dose as 30 mg/kg mouse.

lethality leading to a fully inactive form on modification of five out of ten amino groups. The retention of lethality on modification of amino groups with time is shown in Fig. 4. Modification of one amino group (CT-AI) resulted in loss of only 29% lethal potency, whereas on modification of two (CT-AII), three (CT-AIII) and four (CT-AIV) amino groups the decrease in lethality was 66, 72 and 84%, respectively. Cardiotoxin II with five amino groups modified (CT-AV) was inactive at as high a dose as 30 mg/kg mouse.

Fig. 4. Retention of biological activity on modification of amino groups in cardiotoxin II with 2,4-pentanedione: (●) number of amino groups modified in cardiotoxin II with time, (▲) per cent lethality and (○) per cent protoplast stabilising effect.

Assay of bacterial cell lysis: Modification of amino groups in cardiotoxin II also affected its ability to protect bacterial cells from lysis induced by lysozyme (Fig. 4). Modification of one amino group led to a loss of only 27% of the ability to confer stability on cells. But, further modification involving two, three and four amino groups led to 81, 83 and 83% inactivation, respectively. The time course of bacterial cell lysis in the presence of native and modified derivatives of cardiotoxin II is shown in Fig. 5. The assay of derivatives with more than four amino groups modified could not be carried out because the solubilisation of such

derivatives required inclusion of SDS which in itself inhibits the lysis of bacterial cells.

Fig. 5. Effect of amino group modification by 2,4-pentanedione on stabilisation by cardiotoxin II of *M. lysodeikticus* protoplasts: (○) lysozyme control, (△) native cardiotoxin II plus lysozyme, (□) CT-AI plus lysozyme, (●) CT-AII plus lysozyme, (▲) CT-AIII plus lysozyme, (×) CT-AIV plus lysozyme and (■) 0.01% SDS plus lysozyme.

Discussion

Cardiotoxin II contains side-chains of nine lysine residues, one *N*-terminal α -amino group and two guanido groups of two arginine residues^{1,8} capable of reaction with 2,4-pentanedione. 2,4-Pentanedione can modify side chains of both lysines and arginines^{1,9}. However, the reactivity of the α -amino group has not been considered in particular by earlier authors. The present study on cardiotoxin II reveals that the α -amino group is also modified by the reagent. A molar absorption of $4.2 \times 10^4 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$ at 310 nm was obtained for the reaction product of lysine with 2,4-pentanedione suggesting that both the amino groups (α and ϵ) were modified by the reagent in lysine. However, the spectrum of the lysine derivative exhibited an absorption maximum at 300 nm instead of at 310 nm usually seen for mono-enamine derivatives. The reaction of the α -amino group was indicated by the unavailability of *N*-terminal leucine for dinitrophenylation in fully modified cardiotoxin II.

Under conditions of reaction employed, only amino groups in cardiotoxin II were modified, arginine side chains remaining unaffected. Modification of more than four amino groups led to slow precipitation of the derivatives, possibly due to aggregation. An anionic detergent like SDS

does solubilise such material for further studies, although initial inclusion of SDS in the reaction mixture prevents such derivatives from precipitating out, it also hinders the course of modification. In the presence of SDS, only two amino groups were modified, under conditions in which seven amino groups are modified in 4 h. This is not an unusual effect of SDS, as it has been shown that it is known to diminish the availability of free amino groups of bovine serum albumin, ovalbumin and γ -globulin for the reaction with trinitrobenzenesulphonic acid¹⁹. SDS can form detergent bridges between positively charged ϵ -amino groups located in different loops of the folded peptide chain and the hydrophobic regions of the protein molecule²⁰.

On progressive modification of the amino groups of cardiotoxin, the lethal potency and ability to protect bacterial cells from lysis decay in almost a parallel manner. This means that the amino groups modified which play a role in the matter of acute toxicity as well as the ability to confer stability to bacterial cells from lysis. Perhaps, these free amino groups are involved in binding of cardiotoxin to membranes by electrostatic interactions between positively charged toxin and negatively charged components of membranes.

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